

Figure 2: Veivosaki (The Discussion)

The Pacific employs regional conventions and frameworks to honour Indigenous rights. These regional mechanisms should be drawn on to support Pacific Indigenous full and meaningful participation in the INCs, intersessional, and treaty Conference of Parties (COPs).

[Pacific Islands Declaration on the Prevention of Plastic Pollution and its Impacts:](#)

*“Stressing the importance of incorporating **Indigenous Knowledge Systems, Practices, and Innovations** that have evolved through generations into nature-based solutions for the sustainable conservation of ecosystems.”*

*“Emphasize that **Indigenous Knowledge Systems, Practices, and Innovations** must be an integral part of the solution to the plastics crisis.”*

- [Pacific Regional Framework for the Protection of Traditional Knowledge and Expression of Culture](#)
- [Pacific Plan for Strengthening Regional Cooperation and Integration](#)
- [Pacific Platform for Action on Gender Equality and Women’s Human Rights.](#)

Some important Indigenous Pacific Islands Peoples’ contributions INC negotiations:

- Ensure ecosystems thrive so humans can survive.
- Strengthen culture, well-being, livelihoods, and resilience.
- Respect long-term intergenerational knowledge in place.
- Ensure intra- and intergenerational equity and justice.
- Promote integrated, relational, and holistic worldviews (systems approach).
- Share Indigenous science, knowledge and practices with free, prior, and informed consent.
- Support equitable and inclusive processes, practices, and outcomes.
- Protect the rights and concerns of diverse Indigenous Pacific Islanders.
- Promote zero-waste, safe, restorative materials, products and systems.
- Boost local economies supportive of safe, sustainable, and essential substitutes for plastics.
- Halt harmful and non-essential plastics trade and manufacturing in the region.
- Reject unsafe and unsustainable waste management technologies.

Indigenous Pacific Islanders’ roles are vital in shaping and implementing the GPT and they will greatly contribute to science-policy interfaces. However, they will need support to secure their full, meaningful and empowering participation in the INCs, intersessional, and the COPs.

In the words of a Vanuatuan oral tradition: “Let’s draw our bows back to the past to better reach toward our target in the future”.

Figure 3: “Heke” (The Octopus connecting Pasifika Communities via the Ocean)

- Indigenous peoples in the Pacific are disproportionately affected by plastic pollution because they are located in a region that receives a large amount of plastic waste from other countries due to ocean currents and trade patterns.

- Indigenous peoples in the Pacific have been managing and protecting their ocean for thousands of years, using their traditional knowledge, practices, and values.

- Plastic pollution also undermines the sovereignty and self-determination of indigenous peoples in the Pacific, who have been subjected to colonialism, exploitation, and marginalization for centuries.

- Plastic pollution threatens the health and well-being of indigenous peoples in the Pacific by contaminating their marine resources, damaging their ecosystems, and disrupting their traditional practices.

- Indigenous peoples in the Pacific have been leading the way in finding solutions to plastic pollution, such as banning single-use plastics, promoting circular economies, and implementing community-based initiatives.

- Indigenous peoples in the Pacific have a deep connection to the ocean, which is central to their culture, spirituality, livelihoods, and food security.

- Indigenous peoples in the Pacific have been calling for a global treaty on plastic pollution that recognizes their rights, perspectives, and contributions, and that addresses the entire life cycle of plastics from production to disposal.

- Indigenous peoples in the Pacific have been advocating for a global treaty on plastic pollution that includes elements such as national action plans, binding targets, monitoring and reporting mechanisms, financial and technical support, and public participation.

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Author(s): Rufino Varea¹ and Trisia Farrelly²

Affiliation

¹ Marine Studies, School of Agriculture, Geography, Environment, Ocean and Natural Sciences, The University of the South Pacific, Laucala Campus, Suva, Fiji.
² Political Ecology Research Centre, School of People, Environment and Planning, Massey University, Palmerston North, Aotearoa New Zealand.

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